

The laura in Kom el-Ahmar/ Deir al Qarabin

Secondary source

Entered by Alexandra Konstantinidou

** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Hermits, Christianity, Christian, Basilica, Religious Group, Monastery, Cemetery, Monasticism, Early Christian Monasticism in Egypt, Religious Place

Kom el-Ahmar is a site of Middle Egypt, located on the eastern bank of the Nile, 3 km south of the village of Sharuna. It is situated on the border between the present day expansion of the agricultural area and the desert. This site was initially known for its Pharaonic and Ptolemaic antiquities: the necropolis with rock-cut tombs and the remains of a temple built by Ptolemies I and II. According to the literary sources, the site was the capital of the eighteenth Upper Egyptian nome. Its name, hw.t-nsw, is documented until the Ptolemaic period, but after that time no relevant textual evidence is preserved and the Coptic name of the locality is unknown. In Late Roman/ Byzantine times, a monastic settlement organised as a laura was developed in the desert. The hermits occupied the abandoned Pharaonic rock-cut tombs and constructed new cells at the terraces in front of them. The existing tombs underwent the necessary adjustments so as to function as habitations, workshops, storage rooms, or stables. So far twenty of the tomb-cells have been recorded. The economic and religious centre of the laura was located at the place called Deir el-Qarabin. The northern part of this site includes a large, square, refuge tower and an area with cooking and storage premises, a loom, and traces of wine production. The southern part is occupied by a religious compound including a square burial area flanked by a small chapel to the north and a church to the south. Most probably this was not the cemetery of the monastic community, since there were buried at least thirty individuals, men, women and children. A naturally mummified body was discovered in a somewhat undisturbed tomb, and a C14 analysis of the bones provided a date range between 380 and 560 AD (95.4% probability). The laura also included north of the great concentration of hermitages: i) at c. 0.5km the large, somewhat remote hermitage of el-Ghalida with a monastic cemetery, consisting of at least thirty male burials, and ii) at c. 3km, in a remote location, the hermitage of Deir Abu-Kalba. 900m west of Deir el-Qarabin, a funerary basilica surrounded by a vast cemetery has been unearthed. This complex is situated on a site previously occupied by a Ptolemaic cemetery. Only the foundations of the basilica remain and they include many reused limestone blocks that were extracted from the destroyed Ptolemaic temple. Two building phases have been identified. The earlier building was a three-aisled basilica with a western return aisle, a narthex, a portico, and a rectangular, tripartite sanctuary. In the east, a rectangular annex was added. In the west, at the southern corner of the narthex, there was a staircase towards the roof. In its final state, the naos was divided into five aisles. According to numismatic evidence, the first church was founded during the latter quarter of the fourth century or at the beginning of the fifth century. The second church was a three-aisled basilica, not considerably larger than the first. It was probably erected in the second half of the sixth century. Remodelling during this phase included the demolition of the eastern annex and the western portico. A crypt under the sanctuary, accessible by a staircase, was actually a single chambered tomb, over which the initial church building was constructed. This was probably the tomb of a saint, originally a local hermit. Based on the archaeological and numismatic evidence, the entire settlement at Kom el-Ahmar/Sharuna was probably abandoned in the seventh or eighth century, not as a result of intentional destruction or plundering.

Date Range: 375 CE - 700 CE

Region: Kom el Ahmar

Region tags: Egypt

Kom el Ahmar

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

- ↳ Type of elevation
 - Hill

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: No

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Yes

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

|

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Unknown Saint

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Huber, B. 2018. The Early Christian Cemeteries of Qarara and Sharuna, Middle Egypt. In C. Eger and M. Mackensen (eds) *Death and Burial in the Near East from Roman to Islamic Times. Research in Syria, Lebanon, Jordan and Egypt: 207- 226*. Wiesbaden.

– Source 2: Huber, B. 2017. Sharuna. In R. S. Bagnall, K. Brodersen, C. B. Champion, A. Erskine and S. R. Huebner (eds) *The Encyclopedia of Ancient History*.

– Source 3: Huber, B. 2008. 3000 ans d'histoire à Kom el-Ahmar/Saruna. *ArqueoClub* 9: 24-28.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.trismegistos.org/place/2793>

– Source 1 Description: Trismegistos. An interdisciplinary portal of the ancient world.

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.fundclos.com/en/research/archaeological-research-at-the-kom-al-ahmar-excavation-site-sharuna-middle-egypt-2006-2018/>

– Source 2 Description: The Clos Archaeological Foundation

– Source 3 URL: <https://uni-tuebingen.de/en/12576>

– Source 3 Description: University of Tübingen

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1907, 1913, 1927, 1976-1981, 1984-2018.

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Sharuna/el-Kom el-Ahmar Project

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

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Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

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Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1907, 1913, 1927, 1976-1981, 1984-2018.

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Sharuna/el-Kom el-Ahmar Project

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

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– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Clearing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

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Is the place situated in a rural setting:

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↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: No

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

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– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

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↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– As the result of pillage

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Unknown Saint

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

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Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

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Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

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Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: Fragments of painted plaster, capitals and frieze elements that belonged to the church decoration have been found scattered in the debris and the surrounding area.

↳ On the outside:

– I don't know

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Destroyed

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: Frieze elements

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Unspecified

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: Unspecified

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:
– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

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– No

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↳ Wood

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|

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– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
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↳ On the outside:
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– Field doesn't know

Notes: Destroyed

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

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↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

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↳ Are there statues present:

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↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

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Notes: Frieze elements

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

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↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

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↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Unspecified

↳ Are there paintings present:

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↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

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↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Scattered hermits cells were established in abandoned Pharaonic rock-cut tombs. The slightly distant hermitage of el-Ghalida, which was part of the laura, included a monastic cemetery consisting of at least thirty male burials.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Holy Communion

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unknown (once a week?)

Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes
Notes: Liturgy, prayer

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: Grave-goods are scarce.

↳ Personal effects:

– I don't know

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– No

↳ Other

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Scattered hermits cells were established in abandoned Pharaonic rock-cut tombs. The slightly distant hermitage of el-Ghalida, which was part of the laura, included a monastic cemetery consisting of at least thirty male burials.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

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Notes: Grave-goods are scarce.

Personal effects:

– I don't know

Valuable/precious items:

– No

Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

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↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

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↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: No

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↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

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↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Liturgy, prayer

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Are previously human spirits present:

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Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

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Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Holy Communion

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– No

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

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– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The laura in Kom el-Ahmar/ Deir al Qarabin, Parcak, Sarah. "International Connections at Kom El Ahmar: A Later Period-coptic Period Site in Middle Egypt" 5, no. 4 (December 11, 2013). https://doi.org/10.2458/azu_jaei_v05i4_parcak.